

THE ROLE OF SHEEP AND GOAT HERDING IN FOREST FIRE RISK MANAGEMENT

1. Churra Galega Bragançana sheep grazing in mountain forest areas 2. Goats grazing in oak woods (*Quercus pyrenaica*) 3. Preta de Montesinho goats grazing in a holm oak woodlands (*Quercus rotundifolia*) 4. During the hottest hours, animals enjoy the shade of the forest

THE WHAT AND WHY

Why reintegrate grazing into forests

Throughout their history, Europe's forests, most of which are indigenous, have been extensively grazed. With the advent of modern forest management, traditional practices were gradually devalued, and replaced by models aimed at maximising timber production and direct income. This transition has contributed to the consolidation of a negative perception of the presence of animals in the forest. In the Mediterranean countries, however, the multifunctional nature of forests and the sharp increase in the risk of fire have led to a revaluation of grazing, especially of sheep and goats, as a strategic tool for fire prevention. The contribution of forest grazing to reducing fuel loads, promoting biodiversity, improving soil health and animal welfare is now recognised. This recognition has led to the development of specific grazing support programmes focused on strategic areas.

Keywords: Re-adapting old practices, fuel load reduction, ecosystem services, benefits for animals, Portugal

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

How to implement forest grazing

Promoting grazing in forest areas means recovering a traditional practice, revaluing it and adapting it to today's conditions and challenges, both social and environmental. Grazing can play a strategic role in preventing fires, as a tool for managing combustible biomass and as a means of increasing forest vigilance. Its integration into public policies requires recognition of its environmental and economic value, through appropriate incentives, technical support and specific training for the actors involved. Valuing silvopastoral products, coordination between shepherds and forest owners, and investment in monitoring and scientific knowledge are fundamental conditions for making this model work.

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ADVANTAGES

The Advantages of Forest Grazing

Grazing by small ruminants has several advantages in managing the risk of forest fires, particularly in Mediterranean regions where hot, dry summers and dense vegetation make landscapes highly flammable. The biomass that grows spontaneously in forest areas can be perceived, both as a food resource and, if not used, as a fuel. Without grazing, this biomass tends to accumulate, requiring mechanical intervention or the use of controlled fires. In contrast, the regular presence of animals, whether grazing or staying overnight, reduces this fuel load through ingestion and trampling, creating breaks in the vegetation that limit the intensity and spread of fires. In addition, grazing promotes biodiversity and improves soil quality by encouraging nutrient recycling and biological activity. Economically, grazing is a low-cost alternative to mechanical management or the use of controlled burns, and is particularly effective in remote or rugged areas where the use of machinery is difficult or too costly. Although it doesn't completely replace more intensive treatments that provide an immediate break in the continuity of fuels, grazing makes it possible to extend the interval between these treatments, making land management more sustainable over time. Grazing forest land is also beneficial to the animals that use it. Trees provide supplementary foods such as leaves and fruits, which are essential in times when pasture is less available, reducing the cost of supplements and increasing the food security of the herd. They also provide shade and microclimates that reduce heat stress, significantly improving animal welfare - something that is increasingly important in the context of climate change and frequent heat waves. At the same time, promoting grazing has a positive impact on rural communities by valuing the work of shepherds, reviving traditional practices and combating rural depopulation. This synergy between animal welfare, fire risk reduction and socio-economic resilience makes grazing a valuable tool for the sustainable management of rural areas.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Reintroduction of traditional forest management practices improves forest resilience**
- **Forest grazing reduces fire risk and improves animal welfare**
- **Silvopastoral use involves trade-offs between livestock and forestry production**

Sheep grazing in a meadow at the edge of a Quercus pyrenaica woodlands

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